

A SMALL COMIC GUIDE ON “Dignity Over Display”

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**RESPECT
HER
IMAGE**

Dignity Over Display

Good morning! Today we will learn about the Indecent Representation of Women (Prohibition) Act, 1986.

Madam, why was this Act needed?

Because women were being shown in vulgar and degrading ways in advertisements, posters, books, and films. This law protects the dignity and modesty of women.

So it protects women's image in society?

Exactly. Dignity is part of constitutional values.

SECTION 1 , It gives the detail about :

- * Name of the Act
- * Extends to whole India
- * Came into force on 2nd Oct,1987.

Oo..ok.

Section 1 – Short Title, Extent & Commencement

What is “indecent representation”?

It means showing a woman in an indecent manner
* In a way that harms dignity
* Or corrupts public morality
It includes:
• Advertisements
* Books
* Paintings
* Posters
* Films
* Photographs
* Any visual material

So even a poster can be illegal?

Yes, if it harms dignity or morality.

Section 2 – Definitions

Let`s see

indecent manner • In a way that **harms dignity**

In an indecent manner In a way that harms **dignity** Or corrupts public morality

It includes:

Advertisements Books Paintings Posters

Films Photographs Any Visual Material

Even a Poster
that **harms dignity** or
morality!

Are company ads also covered?

Yes. No advertisement can contain indecent representation of women. Companies are also liable.

Section 3 – Ban on Advertisements

See this types of ads are ban

No Ad Can Show Indecent Representation of Women!

TV Ad

Magazine Ad

Billboard Ad

TV Ad

Online Ad

! Companies Also Liable!

No person shall:

- * Produce
- * Sell
- * Distribute
- * Circulate
- * Send by post

Any material containing indecent representation.

Any exception?

Yes. If it is for:

- * Art
- * Literature
- * Science
- * Learning
- * Public good

Court checks purpose and context.

Section 4 – Ban on Publication & Circulation

How will authorities act?

Section 5 – Search & Seizure

Authorized officer can:

- * Enter premises
- * Search
- * Seize objectionable material

But must follow legal procedure.

Oh! ..Ok

First offence:

- * Up to 2 years imprisonment
- * Fine up to ₹2,000

Second offence:

- * 6 months to 5 years imprisonment
- * Fine ₹10,000 to ₹1,00,000

So punishment becomes stricter for repeat offenders.

Correct

Section 6 – Punishment

If a company commits offence?

Every person in charge is deemed guilty. But they can escape liability if they prove:

- * No knowledge
- * Due diligence taken

Directors and managers may also be liable.

Oo..ok

Section 7 – Offences by Companies

Offence is cognizable — police can investigate.
But generally bailable.

Hmm..

Section 8 – Cognizable & Bailable

Did you asked anything...?

What about officers?

If they act in good faith under this Act, they are protected from legal proceedings.

Section 9 – Protection for Good Faith Action

Central Government makes rules to implement the Act.
Rules must be placed before Parliament.

Oo.

Section 10 – Rule Making Power

In **Chandrakant Kalyandas Kakodkar v. State of Maharashtra**, the Court said obscenity depends on its effect on an ordinary prudent person.

In **Aveek Sarkar v. State of West Bengal**, Supreme Court adopted “contemporary community standards test.” Context matters.

Courts clarified obscenity

Madam, this Act
balances freedom of
expression and dignity.

Very good. Freedom of speech is not
freedom to degrade.

Respect her
image
means
respect the
Constitution

Exactly.

Now write down your homework.

And one thing I want to say;
“ Media must empower, not exploit.”

What happen?

Nothing
ma`am

Wow! It was
very interesting.
THANKYOU
Ma`am.

“Dignity Over Display”

A LEARNING GUIDE

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